

acetylcholinesterase, cholinesterase, and adenosine triphosphatases (both Mg^{++} and $Na^+ - K^+$ ATPases) in brain, blood, and other tissues are study targets. The effect

of pesticides on rice plants, particularly on vegetative growth and on the incidence and varieties of insect infestation, will be investigated. ❧

Seed mats used in screening for gall midge resistance

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In Indonesia we have developed and applied three methods for screening rice varieties for gall midge resistance:

(a) open field screening, (b) continuous screening using colonized midges in the greenhouse, (c) testing inside easy-to-assemble screenhouses in the field. For (c), we started sowing 2 or 3 weeks before an expected peak in insect emergence. Midges were collected with mouth aspirators and released on miniplots in the screenhouses. The method was satisfactory but laborious because the seeds had to be individually sown 2–3 cm apart, 20 seeds/row for each variety. We developed a method for preparing seed mats in advance.

Sowing distances are marked with ink on a sheet of paper, which is then covered by a transparent sheet of plastic, followed by paper tissue. The tissue is brushed with a thin starch solution to make it sticky and transparent. A cardboard strip on which varieties are identified by number is glued to the left side. Seeds are placed one by one on the marked spots. A second tissue is placed on top and gently pressed down with a brush. The sheets are picked up with the plastic underneath them and placed in the sun or in an airconditioned room to dry. The mats are sown on wet soil. Labels are placed beside the numbers on the sheets.

The method provides quick and accurate sowing, reduces the chance of sowing errors in sequence of varieties, prevents moving and loss of seeds when wetted carefully, and makes it easy to sow at distant sites with little instruction. ❧

Seed mats are prepared in advance of a test in Indonesia for varietal resistance to gall midge.

A new mite pest of rice in India

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Spider mites of the genera *Oligonychus* and *Paratetranychus* have previously been reported causing foliage damage to rice in India. During November 1975 plants were observed to have poorly exerted earheads and necrotic leaf sheaths, which were associated with feeding by mites. All mite stages were present between the stem and leaf sheath. Affected glumes had brownish to black lemmata and paleae and shriveled ovaries. The mite has been identified as *Steneotorsonemus spinki* Smiley: Tarsonemid by R. L. Smiley, USDA, Beltsville, Maryland, USA, who says it has been previously collected from rice in Kenya and Taiwan. Panicle deformation has previously been attributed to *S. nodecossas* in Madagascar by V. H. Hai in 1968.

We are continuing research to determine the nature of damage due to *S. spinki*. ❧

Integrated control of *Chilo suppressalis* in Iran

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Since 1972, when *C. suppressalis* was first collected in rice fields in Northern Iran, we have used cultural controls (plowing and flooding fields, removing stubble and host plant weeds, growing short-duration varieties) and selective insecticides against the pest. Results have been good.

In studying biological control of the pest, we have found three parasites and a disease of the insect:

1. *Trichogramma evanescens* (egg parasite)
2. *Apanteles* sp. (larval parasite)
3. *Andralus spinidems* (larval parasite)
4. *Beauveria bassiana* (larval disease)

The research is incomplete. ❧